

EVALUATION OF THE GASTRONOMY TOURISM POTENTIAL OF BEYKOZ DISTRICT BY SWOT ANALYSIS

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Abstract

In this study, in order to determine the gastronomy tourism potential of Beykoz district, located in the province of Istanbul, it was aimed to determine the strengths-weaknesses and opportunities-threats of the district in terms of gastronomy tourism by SWOT analysis. While the population of the study consists of tourism businesses operating in the Beykoz district of Istanbul, the sample of the study consists of 28 business managers and enterprises who voluntarily participated in the study among the tourism businesses operating in this district. In the study, interview technique, one of the qualitative data collection methods, was used and content analysis was applied to the obtained data. When the findings obtained as a result of the study are examined, it is seen that the strength of the district is its geographical location, its weakness is the lack of promotion, advertising and socio-cultural structure, its biggest opportunity is that it has coasts to the Marmara and Black Sea and is located on the Bosphorus, and its threats are that investors in the region have not been able to adopt the concept of gastronomy tourism. For future studies, research can be done based on the SWOT data obtained from the study, and studies are recommended especially for local, indigenous products and products with regional geographical indication potential. It is thought that as the number of such studies increases, an element of attraction can be created in the region and a destination image can be created.

Keywords: Tourism; Gastronomy; Gastronomy tourism; Beykoz; Istanbul.

AVALIAÇÃO DO POTENCIAL DO TURISMO GASTRONÔMICO DO DISTRITO DE BEYKOZ POR ANÁLISE SWOT

Resumo

Neste estudo, para determinar o potencial do turismo gastronômico do distrito de Beykoz, localizado na província de Istanbul, pretendeu-se determinar os pontos fortes-fracos e as oportunidades-ameaças do distrito em termos de turismo gastronômico através da análise SWOT. A amostra do estudo consiste em 28 gestores de negócios e empresas que participaram voluntariamente no estudo entre as empresas de turismo que operam no distrito de Beykoz, em Istanbul, sendo a população do estudo o tal de empresas de turismo que operam neste contexto. No estudo foi utilizada a técnica de entrevista, um dos métodos de coleta de dados qualitativos, e a análise de conteúdo foi aplicada aos dados obtidos. Quando se examinam os resultados obtidos no estudo, verifica-se que o ponto forte do distrito é a sua localização geográfica, o seu ponto fraco é a falta de promoção, publicidade e estrutura sociocultural, a sua maior oportunidade é ter costas ligadas ao Mar de Mármara e ao Mar Negro e está localizado no Bósforo, e a ameaça é que os investidores da região não tenham conseguido adotar o conceito de turismo gastronômico. Para estudos futuros, pesquisas podem ser feitas com base nos dados SWOT obtidos no estudo, sendo recomendados estudos especialmente para produtos locais, indígenas e produtos com potencial de indicação geográfica regional. Pensa-se que à medida que aumenta o número de tais estudos, pode ser criado um elemento de atração na região e uma imagem do destino pode ser criada.

Palavras-chave: Guia Turístico Profissional; Produtividade; Desenvolvimento de escala; Método Misto.

EVALUACIÓN DEL POTENCIAL DEL TURISMO GASTRONÓMICO EN EL DISTRITO DE BEYKOZ MEDIANTE ANÁLISIS FODA

Resumen

En este estudio; Para determinar el potencial del turismo gastronómico del distrito de Beykoz, ubicado en la provincia de Estambul, el objetivo fue determinar las fortalezas, debilidades y oportunidades-amenazas del distrito en términos de turismo gastronómico mediante un análisis FODA. La muestra del estudio está formada por 28 directivos de empresas y empresas que participaron voluntariamente en el estudio entre las empresas turísticas que operan en el distrito Beykoz de Estambul, siendo la población del estudio el total de empresas de turismo que operan en este contexto. En el estudio se utilizó la técnica de la entrevista, uno de los métodos de recolección de datos cualitativos, y se aplicó el análisis de contenido a los datos obtenidos. Al examinar los hallazgos obtenidos como resultado del estudio se ve que la fortaleza del distrito es su ubicación geográfica, su debilidad es la falta de promoción, publicidad y estructura sociocultural, su mayor oportunidad es que cuenta con costas al Mármara y al Mar Negro y está situada en el Bósforo, y su amenaza es que los inversores de la región no han podido adoptar el concepto de turismo gastronómico. Para estudios futuros, se pueden realizar investigaciones basadas en los datos FODA obtenidos del estudio, y se recomiendan estudios especialmente para productos locales, indígenas y productos con potencial de indicación geográfica regional. Se piensa que a medida que aumente el número de estudios de este tipo, se podrá crear un elemento de atracción en la región y se podrá crear una imagen de destino.

Palabras clave: Turismo; Gastronomía; Turismo gastronómico; Beykoz; Estambul.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is known that tourism activities, which consisted of the trio of sea, sand and sun in the perception of individuals in the past, have changed over time by gaining different dimensions. The interest in tourism activities is increasing day by day as a result of factors such as the increase in purchasing power and leisure time, the emergence of new tourism trends and the curiosity of people about these trends.

Today, awareness of gastronomy and understanding how important it is for destinations is finally based on gastronomy tourism, and it has become a curious tourism trend of recent days, just like other types of tourism. Gastronomy is an important element in reflecting the culture of the regions and is one of the most important components in creating a sense of belonging and originality to that region (Fuste-Forne, 2017).

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Experiencing elements such as the eating and drinking cultures of different regions and local dishes has become an important tourism motivation for individuals, and gastronomy elements are now seen as an effective factor in traveling. So much so that the rapid increase in gastronomic tourism activities has reached not only intercity dimensions, but also countries and even intercontinental dimensions.

In short, gastronomy tourism, which can be explained as the tourism movement that people do to wonder and experience the culinary cultures, food and beverages in different regions, has become an important tool in creating added value not only for tourists but also for curious regions.

The increase in the interest in tourism activities and the diversification of tourism activities have increased the demand for tourism, and destinations have entered into different searches in order to meet the demands and expectations, and to market the elements of tourist attraction (Çelik, 2018). Tourism activities, which previously came from the trio of sea, sand and sun, are now differentiated and divided into many sub-branches (Türk, 2021).

One of these, gastronomic tourism, has become a popular type of tourism that emerged with the curiosity and interest of different foods and beverages in different regions (Cömert & Durlu-Özkaya, 2014). So much so that food and beverage businesses create a competitive advantage by providing great value to touristic destinations in order to support gastronomic tourism activities (Şengül, Türkay & Yılmaz, 2022).

The concept of gastronomy, which deals with food and beverage culture scientifically and artistically, has become integrated with tourism and has now become an important element for the promotion of cities, regions, in short, touristic destinations (Küçükaltan, 2009; Özkaya, Sünnetçioğlu & Can, 2013). Each culture creates its own gastronomic infrastructure with the materials, techniques, recipes, aromas, serving styles and even eating and drinking styles specific to the area (Araujo, Braga & Gonçalves, 2022).

Regions have created added value for gastronomy tourism by using existing gastronomic elements, used these elements in tourism marketing and started to create economic benefits (Hall & Sharples, 2003; Zainal, Zali & Kassim, 2010). Since the eating and drinking cultures, rituals and ceremonies of societies constitute an important part of the culture that reflects that region, it is also interesting in terms of learning the unknowns of the regions (Şahin, 2016).

The competition between destinations requires the creation of new touristic products and the continuity of these products, and also requires destinations to protect their culturally local elements. Tourism destinations can make a difference and come to the fore in the tourism market only when they progress through these two basic steps (Şahin, 2019). In this direction, it is possible to say that the gastronomic tourism movement has a strong role in economic development and provides significant added value to touristic regions (İbiş, 2020).

Beykoz, located on the Anatolian side of Istanbul, is one of the important districts of Istanbul, which stands out with its history, nature and location. It has an important tourism potential with its shores to the Bosphorus and the Black Sea, its nature that offers blue and green together, and its ease of transportation. In terms of eating and drinking

culture, the existence of gastronomic products specific to the district and the living of individuals from every region of the country in the district are interesting in terms of gastronomy tourism potential.

With the study, which aims to determine the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz district with SWOT analysis, it is aimed to support the promotion of regional cuisine culture by determining the current gastronomic tourism dynamics of the district, revealing its strengths and weaknesses and opportunities-threats.

Studies that enable the prediction and detection of gastronomy tourism potential on a regional basis generally focus on seaside regions that are already tourism destinations. This study is based on the Beykoz district, which is relatively less of a touristic area in Istanbul but is thought to have serious potential. The fact that there is currently no theoretical and experimental study in the region has led to this study in order to fill the gap. In this case, it reveals the unique value and originality of the work.

The purpose of this research study is to determine the gastronomy tourism potential of Beykoz district, to emphasize the elements that are important for the gastronomy tourism of the region, and to determine and reveal the contributions of these elements to the destination in terms of gastronomy tourism. What can be done to use these as marketing elements? Examining Beykoz district, which has a significant tourism potential, in terms of gastronomy tourism is important for the economic development of the region and providing added value to the region.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Beykoz District

It is known that one of the most basic physiological needs necessary for the continuity of life is the need for nutrition. The need for nutrition, which has been known to exist since the existence of humanity and is intertwined with social phenomena, also plays an important role in the shaping of cultural elements (Karaca & Altun, 2017). It is known that the gastronomy discipline, which deals with the relationship between food, nutrition and culture, has the meaning of 'stomach law' as a term.

Gastronomy, which consists of the Greek words gaster (stomach) and nomas (law), is explained as a discipline that makes regional or national cuisines different from each other and deals with the food and beverages, eating cultures and cuisine-specific techniques of a particular country or region (Zengin & Gürkan, 2019). Turkish Language Association (2022) gastronomy; "Healthy, well-arranged, pleasant and delicious cuisine, food order and system," he explains. Based on the definitions of gastronomy, it is known that gastronomy covers the preparation and presentation of all edible materials and examines the local food and beverage culture and local food and beverage (Ongun, İnanır & Kiliç, 2019).

Gastronomic tourism, it is the tourism movement of tourists in order to taste the foods and beverages specific to different regions, to learn about the food preparation stages and the culinary culture of that region (Hall, Mitchell & Sharpless, 2003). Gastronomic tourism, also known as culinary tourism or food tourism (Barroco & Augusto, 2016);

It is expressed as individuals experiencing the food and beverages of a region and living that culture at the same time.

Understanding the food cultures of destinations, learning about local food producers, food festivals and all areas of gastronomy constitute the main subject of gastronomy tourism (Çavuşoğlu & Çavuşoğlu, 2018). It is a known fact that gastronomic tourism provides significant benefits for the development of touristic destinations (Kargiglioğlu & Karabacak, 2017).

Individuals now list what foods they should taste as well as the list of things to see in their destination while planning their vacation. The desire to experience the cuisine of a region in regional or local terms is seen as one of the most important reasons for participating in gastronomic tourism activities (Akbaba & Kendirci, 2016).

Gastronomic tourism, whose popularity is increasing day by day, has taken place in the programs of many tour and travel guides and has become an important tool in contributing to destinations economically (Birdir & Akgöl, 2015; Mol & Varlık, 2019). In this direction, it is extremely important for destinations to preserve their local food cultures and to make these cultures an attraction for tourists and to create their marketing policies in this direction (Özdemir, 2008).

All regions in our country's geography have their own unique foods and beverages, eating and drinking cultures and rituals. The most important factors in shaping the culinary culture of a region are climate, geography, agriculture and livestock potential and religious beliefs, etc. are factors.

Beykoz district is a popular district located in the northern part of Istanbul, which fully embodies the green and blue, and is known for its rural settlements, forests and groves as well as the central part. The Black Sea is located in the north of the district, Üsküdar in the south, the Bosphorus in the west and Şile district in the east (Tarakçı et al., 2012). Beykoz district has many historical buildings as well as neighborhoods with touristic potential. Kanlıca, famous for its yogurt, Paşabahçe, identified with glass and glassmaking, historical fishing town Anadolu Kavağı, Anadolu Hisarı, known for its castle, Polonezköy are among the most well-known neighborhoods of the district.

The district contains many touristic attraction elements with its famous groves, recreation areas, historical mansions, fountains, century-old trees, in short, green and blue. Based on all these factors, it is interesting to examine the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz and to reveal this potential. Table 1 includes some similar studies aimed at determining the potential of gastronomy tourism using SWOT analysis.

Table 1. Similar studies on the potential of gastronomy tourism.

Author(S)	Year	Subject
Gamze Eryılmaz, Halil Can Orhan	2021	The Evaluation of Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Elazığ Province with SWOT Analysis
Okan TÜRK	2021	Gastronomy Tourism Potential and SWOT Analysis of the City of Muş
Mustafa Akturfan, Zeynep Çınar, Esat Özata	2022	Evaluation of the Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Karaman Province by Swot Analysis
Banu Zencir	2022	The Evaluation of Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Afyonkarahisar Province Through SWOT Analysis
Ümit Sormaz, Mustafa Yılmaz, Esat Özata, Cemile Büyükyıldırım	2023	Evaluation of the Gastronomic Tourism Potential of Burdur Province By Swot Analysis
Gülçin Algan Özkök, Orhan Mutu, Ümit Sormaz	2023	Evaluation of the Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Silivri District Within The Scope of Sustainable Tourism By Swot Analysis
Ümit Sormaz, Nurudin Kırırallyev, Sapargül Turdubekova, Nadira Turganbaeva, Dinara İsokava, Gülmira Samatova	2023	Evaluation of The Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Bishkek Within The Scope of Sustainable Tourism with SWOT Analysis
Hilal Öz, Ümit Sormaz, H. Ferhan Nizamlioğlu, Gürkan Akdağ	2023	Evaluation of the Gastronomy Tourism Potential of Hatay Province with SWOT Analysis

Source: own elaboration.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Purpose and Model of the Research

In this study, which aims to determine the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz district of Istanbul, it is aimed to reveal the internal factors such as the strengths and weaknesses of the district, and external factors such as opportunities and threats.

In the study, in order to determine the potential of gastronomic tourism, case study and SWOT analysis method, which are qualitative research methods, were used because of the necessity of determining the opinions of the managers in the tourism enterprises in the district. Yıldırım and Şimsek (2013) case study; Based on the idea that the situations related to the subjects examined may differ, he explained that it is not based on the general interpretation of the findings, but on the basis of transferring them through examples and experiences so that similar situations can be detected more easily.

SWOT analysis is a method that enables strategies to be developed in this context by revealing internal factors such as advantages and disadvantages of a certain situation, product or element compared to competitors, and external factors such as opportunities and threats (Karadeniz, Kandır & Önal, 2007). SWOT as word structure; It consists of the English initials of the words Advantages (Strengths), Disadvantages (Weaknesses), Opportunities (Opportunities) and Threats (Doğdubay & Karan, 2015). SWOT analysis has been frequently used to develop future-oriented strategies in order to determine and analyze competitiveness in studies in the field of tourism since the 1990s (Yan & Wang, 2021).

3.2. Population and Sample of the Research

Tourism businesses or managers operating in Istanbul constitute the universe of the study. The numerical data of the enterprises that make up the research universe are given

in Table 1 (Istanbul Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2022).

Table 1. Tourism, Food & Beverage Businesses Operating in Istanbul.

Business Document Type	Number of Businesses
Has Tourism Operation Certificate	1246
Has Tourism Investment Certificate	72
TOTAL	1318

Source: Istanbul Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2022.

In the study, the deliberate sampling method was preferred in the selection of the sample. The main purpose of this is; The fact that the study was carried out in Beykoz district and the study was limited to this district. The sample consists of people working in managerial positions in businesses related to tourism and food and beverage businesses operating in Beykoz district of Istanbul, holding a tourism operation certificate.

Volunteering is essential in the study and in this context, 28 businesses/28 managers formed the sample of the research, taking into account the personnel who are in the managerial position of the tourism and food and beverage businesses in the district. Teyin et al. (2021) stated that the sample size should be at least 15 in qualitative studies. In this respect, the number of samples was deemed sufficient to represent the study population.

3.3. Data Collection Method and Tool

In the study, the structured interview technique, a qualitative data collection technique, was used. This technique is frequently used because of its aspects that allow working on smaller sample groups, obtaining the desired data completely and in detail, and asking questions to each participant under equal conditions (Tümüklü, 2000). The structured form used to obtain the data in the study is one of the forms applied in previous similar studies (Durgun, 2007; Yeşiltaş, Çeken & Öztürk, 2009; Birdir, Karakan & Çolak, 2015; Deniz & Atışman, 2017; Özkan, Kasap & Sormaz, 2019). compiled and prepared. In the first part of the questionnaire, which consists of two parts, there are statements containing demographic information and business and activity information. In the second part, there are open-ended questions aiming to measure the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz district.

The data were obtained by conducting face-to-face interviews with the relevant managerial personnel forming the sample between 29.08.2022 and 22.09.2022. Content analysis was applied to the obtained data in order to systematically address and analyze the views, and the findings were divided into themes and codes based on the results of the content analysis.

3.4. Data Analysis

Frequency analysis was applied to the demographic data obtained from the interview surveys in the SPSS package program. The opinion expressions obtained from the form were analyzed with content analysis.

3.5. Data Security, Ethics and Limitations of the Research

In the creation of the interview form used to obtain the data in the study, similar studies carried out before were used. In this respect, the compilation of previously used and tested questions contributes to data reliability. There may be differences in the validity-reliability of qualitative studies compared to quantitative studies (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013).

Reliability means that the same results are obtained when the scale is applied to the same sample at different times under the same conditions (Başkale, 2016). Validity, on the other hand, is defined as the degree to which the scale measures what it is intended to measure (Ural & Kılıç, 2005). In terms of objective evaluation of the data obtained as a result of the interview, care was taken to include the people who will participate in the interview voluntarily.

Ethics committee permission required in order to obtain the data used in the study; Doğuş University Ethics Committee was taken with the date 08.02.2022 and the decision/number of 2022/12.

This study is limited only to the Beykoz district that constitutes the sample and the data obtained through the interview form.

4 FINDINGS

The demographic information of the participants, who constitute the sample of the study, is given in Table 2. When the demographic characteristics of the participants were examined in terms of gender, it was seen that 25% of the participants who voluntarily participated in the study were female and 75% were male. Again, 53.6% of the participants were 31-45 years old, 25% were 46-60 years old, 17.9% were 61 years old and over, 3.6% were 18-30 years old. It was observed that 42.9% of them were secondary school graduates, 28.6% undergraduate, 14.3% primary school, 10.7% associate degree and 3.6% postgraduate degree.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants.

Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Female	7	25
Male	21	75
Age		
18-30 years	1	3,6
31-45 years	15	53,6
46-60 years	7	25
61 years and older	5	17,9
Education		
Primary School	4	14,3
Secondary School	12	42,9
High School	3	10,7
Associate Degree	8	28,6
Graduate/Postgraduate	1	3,6
TOTAL	28	100

Source: The author derived from study data.

When the professional information of the participants is examined, 57.1% have a professional diploma, 60.7% work in the position of business manager, 32.1% have been working in the sector for 21-30 years and 39.3% are currently employed. It has been determined that they have been working in their respective places for 6-10 years (Table 3).

Table 3. Professional Information Regarding the Participants.

Vocational Education Level	n	%
Professional diploma	16	57,1
Mastery/journeyman certificate	2	7,1
Vocational course completion certificate	4	14,3
Does not have a professional certificate	6	21,4
Position in Business	n	%
Business owner	11	39,3
Business manager	17	60,7
Working Time in the Industry	n	%
less than 5 years	3	10,7
6-10 years	5	17,9
11-20 years	8	28,6
21-30 years	9	32,1
31 years and above	3	10,7
Current Working Time in Business	n	%
less than 5 years	8	28,6
6-10 years	11	39,3
11-20 years	8	28,6
21-30 years	1	3,6
TOTAL	28	100

Source: The author derived from study data.

A total of 28 tourism businesses (100%) were included in the study, including 6 hotel businesses (21.4%) and 22 restaurant businesses (78.6%) operating in Beykoz district. Relevant businesses are included in the study voluntarily and they are businesses that have tourism operation certificate. When these enterprises are examined, it is seen that 60.7% of them are in the status of independent enterprises, 50% of them have 1-3 branches and 35.7% of them have been serving for 5-9 years (Table 4).

Table 4. General Information on Businesses.

	Hotel Businesses		Restaurant Businesses	
Business' Ownership Structure	n	%	n	%
National/International Chained	4	66,7	7	31,8
Independent	2	33,3	15	68,2
Business' Number of Branches	n	%	n	%
No branches	0	0	6	21,4
1-3 branches	1	16,7	11	42,9
4 or more branches	5	83,3	5	35,7
Year of Service	n	%	n	%
1-4 years	1	16,7	5	22,7
5-9 years	2	33,3	8	36,4
10-14 years	2	33,3	7	31,8
15 years and above	1	16,7	2	9,1
TOTAL	6	100	22	100

Source: The author derived from study data.

When the personnel information and management styles of the enterprises included in the study were examined, it was seen that 78.6% of the enterprises had 10 or more personnel, and 57.1% were managed by the business manager and department heads (Table 5).

Table 5. Business' Administrative Structure and Personnel Information.

Business' Number of Personnel Working	n	%
less than 10 people	6	21,4
10 people and above	22	78,6
Business Management	n	%
Managed by the owner(s)	11	39,3
Managed by the business manager & dept heads	16	57,1
TOTAL	28	100

Source: The author derived from study data.

Table 7. Strengths and Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of Gastronomy Tourism in Beykoz District.

Strengths	n	%
S1. Geographical location of the county.	24	88,9
S2. Potential for gastronomic tourism due to the presence of tastes unique to the district.	22	81,5
S3. Suitability of natural and cultural resources for alternative tourism types.	16	59,3
S4. Transportation facilities.	12	44,4
S5. Finding the historical texture and past of the district.	7	25,9
S6. Being in Istanbul, where the tourist population is high.	6	22,2
S7. Having a high number of qualified and luxury restaurants, thus having a qualified workforce.	2	7,4
Weaknesses	n	%
W1. Inadequate promotion and advertisement of foods with potential for gastronomic tourism.	18	66,7
W2. The sharpness of the socio-cultural structure of the people living in the district.	17	65,4
W3. District-specific foods are not served in restaurants in the region.	9	34,6
W4. Due to the dense population of Istanbul, the operating capacities cannot meet the demand.	5	19,2
W5. The fact that the business managers in the district could not adopt the gastronomic tourism activities.	4	15,4
W6. Lack of tourism awareness of the people of the district and prejudice against tourists.	1	3,8
Opportunities	n	%
O1. Due to the location of the district, it is located in the Bosphorus, it has coasts to Marmara and Black Sea.	23	82,1
O2. Easy to reach both by land and sea.	22	78,6
O3. Continuation of the traditional festivals held in the district, the feasibility of promoting gastronomic products in these festivals.	19	67,9
O4. Implementation of other alternative tourism types that can be combined with gastronomic tourism in the district.	12	42,9
O5. Natural beauties of the district.	8	28,6
O6. Supportive perspective of local government on gastronomic tourism activities.	4	15,4
Threats	n	%
T1. The fact that the concept of gastronomic tourism is not adopted by the investors in the district.	27	96,4
T2. The fact that the gastronomy products in the district have not yet been registered such as geographical marking.	23	82,1
T3. The fact that the menus of the businesses operating in the district do not offer the tastes of the district.	18	64,3
T4. Due to the increasing population in Istanbul, the natural environment and resources are decreasing day by day.	15	53,6
T5. Existing businesses are not managed by professionals.	7	25
T6. Lack of publicity in the county.	2	7,1

Source: The author derived from study data.

The results of the content analysis of the information obtained through the interview form regarding the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz district are given in Table 6. When the data obtained as a result of the content analysis on the strengths of Beykoz district are examined, the main themes are the geographical location of the district (88.9%), the district's unique flavors (81.5%), the district's suitability for alternative tourism activities (59.3%), transportation facilities (44.4%), the historical and natural structure of the region (25.9%), the intense tourist potential in Istanbul (22.2%) and the high number of qualified enterprises in the region (7.4%).

Easy access to Beykoz district, both by road and by sea, is a very important factor for tourism activities. In their study, Akturfan, Çınar and Özata (2022) referred to the fact that the city is on the highway route and the ease of transportation among the strengths of Karaman province.

The results obtained from the study are compatible with this study. Local foods such as centuries-old Kanlıca yoghurt, Beykoz kebab, Beykoz trotter are important in terms of gastronomy tourism. In his study analyzing the gastronomy tourism potential of Muş province, Zencir (2021) stated that the most important strength of the city is the local food culture of the region. That results are compatible with this study.

The region-specific dishes of Beykoz district constitute the strengths of its gastronomy tourism potential. Again, the district provides suitable conditions for alternative tourism activities with its forests, groves, shores to the Bosphorus and historical structures. It will be possible to contribute to the development of gastronomy tourism in the district by presenting tourism activities that can be done in the region and gastronomic tourism activities together.

On the other hand, the fact that Istanbul attracts more tourists day by day, contributes to the development of the district, and that the restaurants in the region appeal to the upper segments structurally and that they are qualified businesses are the supporting elements of the district in terms of gastronomic tourism.

When the data obtained as a result of the content analysis on the weaknesses of Beykoz district are examined, firstly, it is encountered with an opinion statement that the advertisement and promotion of the foods with potential for gastronomy tourism is not done well (66.7%). Özata et al. (2023) in their study analyzing the gastronomy tourism potential of Burdur province, stated that one of the weaknesses of the region is the lack of coordination with local governments.

The results of the conducted study are compatible with the results of this study. Similarly, Eryılmaz and Orhan (2022), in their study investigating the gastronomy tourism potential of Elazığ province, touched upon the fact that local stakeholders and investors were insensitive to gastronomy tourism. It is seen that the results obtained from this study and the study of Eryılmaz and Orhan are also compatible. It is striking that the socio-cultural structure of the people living in the district is one of the weak aspects of the district (65.4%).

The main reason for this is that the people living in the district are socio-economically composed of both the upper class and the working class, and the distribution of this

structure is separated by a sharp line. This situation explains how important the perspective of the public is in tourist and tourism activities. Another weakness of the district in terms of gastronomic tourism is that the foods specific to the district are not included in the menus of the luxury restaurants in the district (34.6%).

The fact that the current operating capacities of the enterprises cannot meet the demand (19.2%) and that the business managers have not adopted gastronomic tourism activities (15.4%) are also among the weaknesses. Finally, the tourism activities of a certain segment living in the district and the prejudiced point of view towards tourists (3.8%) are also weak points in the light of the information obtained from the interview form for the gastronomic tourism activities of the district.

Luxury and quality restaurants in the district provide an important infrastructure for gastronomic tourism activities. Increasing cooperation with these businesses will contribute greatly to the development of the region in terms of gastronomy, and the inclusion of district-specific flavors in the business menus is important in terms of preserving our traditional culture and transferring it to future generations.

When the results of the content analysis of the information obtained through the interview form in determining the opportunities for the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz district are examined, the main themes are the location of the district, having coasts to the Marmara and Black Seas (82.1%), the availability of transportation opportunities (78.6%), the fact that the district is still located.

The fact that there are many ongoing traditional festivals and the importance of these festivals in terms of gastronomic tourism (67.9%), the fact that Beykoz district hosts alternative tourism activities with different structures that can be integrated with gastronomic tourism (42.9%), the natural and natural beauties of the district (28.6%) and local governments' moderate perspective on gastronomy tourism (15.4%).

In their study conducted in 2024, Algan-Özkök, Mutu and Sormaz (2024) mentioned that among the opportunities of Silivri district are the region's seaside location, organizing gastronomy festivals, and the existence of touristic facilities and historical buildings. Similarly, in the study, the coastline of Beykoz district to the sea, the organization of touristic festivals in the district, the existence of touristic facilities and historical buildings were explained as opportunities.

Similarly, Öz et al. (2023) emphasized that the geographical location of the region should be considered as an opportunity in their study where they identified the gastronomy tourism of Hatay province with SWOT analysis. The results of the study are parallel to the conducted study.

The biggest reason why Beykoz is introduced as the pearl of the Bosphorus is, of course, that it has a long throat strip. Thanks to this feature, there are very high-quality restaurants, especially on the ridges of the Bosphorus or in the mansions. Likewise, being at the intersection of the Black Sea region and the Bosphorus, it contains many important touristic components with its large groves and forests, and its historical texture. By structuring the existing resources in the eye of gastronomy tourism, it will contribute to the development of the region and add value in terms of gastronomy tourism.

When the interview data obtained regarding the threat factors of the gastronomy tourism potential of the district are examined, the main themes are that the gastronomic tourism is not adopted by the investors in the district (96.4%), the gastronomy products in the district do not have registrations such as geographical marking yet (82.1%), the existing existing in the district.

Due to the fact that the menus of the enterprises do not include the foods specific to Beykoz district (64.3%), the nature of the district is due to the increasing population and crowding. It is seen that it consists of opinions such as the deterioration of the provincial and natural structure (53.6%), the management of the businesses operating in the district by non-professionals (25%), and the lack of publicity in the district (7.1%).

In their study where Sormaz et al. (2023) analyzed Bishken's gastronomy tourism potential, they emphasized the lack of a qualified workforce trained in tourism education, vehicle traffic and the quality of restaurants as threats. In this study, where the gastronomy tourism potential of Beykoz district is investigated, the threats that cannot be employed in the region by qualified workforce, traffic problems due to the crowding of Istanbul, and the poor quality of food-beverage and accommodation establishments in the region are shared.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The scientific study of gastronomy includes detailed information about foods and eating and drinking, cooking practices and cultural facts about eating and drinking. When considered within the scope of tourism activities, the phenomenon that appears as gastronomic tourism is important in terms of the activities of tourism destinations and being an attraction factor (Teyin et al., 2021).

It has greatly contributed to the emergence of gastronomy tourism as a type of tourism, in which gastronomy plays an important role in the choice of destination that people make before they go on vacation (Çelik & Aksoy, 2017; Cute, Tatlı & Kızıldemir, 2021). Culinary cultures and the food and beverage cultures of the countries that have an important place in terms of tourism provide an important infrastructure in terms of tourism activities (Du Randi 2006).

As a result of the interviews with the participants who voluntarily participated in the study, the strengths of Beykoz district are: "The geographical location of the district, the potential for gastronomy tourism due to the presence of tastes unique to the district, the availability of natural and cultural resources for alternative tourism types, the transportation possibilities of the district, the historical texture and history of the district".

It consists of the opinions of "being located in the province of Istanbul, where the tourist density is high, and having qualified and luxurious restaurants in the district", while their weaknesses are "not advertising and promoting the foods that have potential for gastronomic tourism, the socio-cultural structure of the people of the district, the fact that the district-specific foods are not served in the restaurants in the region.

The inadequacy of the operating capacities due to the dense population and demand, the failure of the business managers to adopt gastronomic tourism activities, the lack of gastronomic tourism awareness of the people of the district and their prejudice against tourists. button is visible.

According to the participants, "due to the location of the district, it is located on the Bosphorus, it has coasts to the Marmara and Black Seas, the traditional festivals are still continuing in the district, the existence of alternative tourism types that can be applied together with gastronomy tourism in the district, the natural beauties of the district and a supportive view of the gastronomic tourism activities of local governments". While evaluating factors such as "the angle" as the opportunities that Beykoz district has.

The concept of gastronomy tourism has not yet been adopted by the investors in the district, the gastronomic products in the district do not have registrations such as geographical marking, the menus of the restaurants operating in the district do not include district-specific foods, the increasing population harms the natural environment and resources, the existing businesses are not managed by professionals, and the promotion in the district.

They stated the factors of 'deficiency' as the existing potential threat elements of the Beykoz district. It is an important issue to provide added value to the district in terms of sustainability and gastronomy, and the registration of products that support the gastronomic tourism potential of Beykoz district, such as centuries old Kanlıca yogurt, Beykoz kebab, Karakulak juice, Paça ice cream, Beykoz trotter, by carrying out geographical indication studies and increasing promotional activities. As a result of the results obtained, in order to develop the gastronomic tourism of Beykoz district and to benefit from the existing potential;

- Increasing the effectiveness of advertising and promotion activities of region-specific food and local products in the district,
- Taking the geographical indication registration of products such as centuries old Kanlıca yoghurt, Beykoz kebab, Beykoz trotter, Karakulak juice under protection,
- Include more frequent flavors unique to the district in the menus of the businesses in the district,
- Developing strategies that will enable the people of the region to participate in and benefit from tourism activities,
- Establishing cooperation with local governments in order to create tourism awareness among the people of the district,
- Collaborating with the Culinary, Gastronomy and Tourism departments of existing universities in the district, both academically and socially,
- Providing trainings to increase the qualifications of the personnel of the businesses that continue their activities and that will start new, and cooperating with Non-Governmental Organizations, Public Education Centers and Universities for these trainings,
- Natural, historical, etc. owned by the district. adoption of sustainable tourism activities for the protection of beauties,
- Cultural tours, Bosphorus tours etc. organized in Istanbul. including Beykoz district in touristic tours,
- Providing the necessary incentives and support by local governments for all activities that support gastronomic tourism activities Recommendations can be made.

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Term	Definition	Author
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	x
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	x
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	x
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	x
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	x
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	x
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x
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Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	x
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